

How does increased salination jeopardize the floral diversity of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh?

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the responses of the flora of the *Sundarbans* mangrove of Bangladesh to increased salination. Empirical data was used to identify the adverse effect of salinity. Based on the respondents' perceptions, it was found that significant off-site occurs in the previous freshwater rivers and canals. The pioneer *Sundari* trees (*Heritiera fomes*) are affected by Dieback disease due to increased salinity. Dieback contributes to the loss of canopy coverage and produces weak crowns, with sparse foliage and a good proportion of dead twigs and branches. It was revealed that the declining trend of the abundance of *Nypa* palm (*Nypa fruticans*) and Mangrove Date Palm (*Phoenix paludosa*) was observed in their historical habitat areas. The respondents opined that Keora (*Sonneratia apetala*) and Bain (*Avicennia Officinalis*) replace *Sundari* (*Heritiera fomes*), Bain (*Avicennia Officinalis*), Kakra (*Bruguiera gymnorhiza*), Passur (*Xylocarpus mekongensis*) and Dhondul tree (*Xylocarpus granatum*) species. Consequently, the species composition, species richness, natural regeneration, and vertical and horizontal structure of the mangrove are changing due to increased salinity.

Keywords: Climate change, Sundarbans mangrove, increased salination, pioneer species, mangrove palm, species composition

Introduction

Bangladesh is confronting both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts every year (Mukhopadhyay *et al.* 2022; Chakraborty 2023; Khan 2019, Chowdhury *et al.* 2020; Haque *et al.* 2020; Ali *et al.* 2019; Hasnat *et al.* 2020; Chiba *et al.* 2017; Alam *et al.* 2020; Billah 2018; Dastagir 2015; Rahman 2020; Rahman 2021 a, b; Rahman *et al.* 2021; Rahman 2022). The *Sundarbans* Delta is struggling with multiple climatic hazards like tropical cyclones, storm surges, and salinization (Chakraborty 2023; Tuladhar 2023; Samanta *et al.* 2021; Visions 2023; Chakraborty *et al.* 2023). Most of the rivers of Bangladesh flow from north to south, silting up the mangroves delta and draining into the Bay of Bengal (van Maren *et al.* 2023; Hossain *et al.* 2023; Bandyopadhyay *et al.* 2023). The mangrove is a transitional territory between the freshwater rivers originating from the Ganges and the Bay of Bengal (Das 2023; Subramanian *et al.* 2023; Jayanthi *et al.* 2023; Hossain *et al.* 2023).

Among climatic stressors, salinization is more prominent in the Sundarbans mangrove due to its long-lasting nature of effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d; Bhowmick *et al.* 2016; Dasgupta *et al.* 2010; Ahmed *et al.* 2022; Ahmed *et al.* 2023). Therefore, the study aimed to assess the responses of the flora of the *Sundarbans* mangrove of Bangladesh to increased salination.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from Forest Department. Local people were personally interviewed to identify the flora. A focus group discussion was done incorporating foresters, environmentalists, botanists and conservationists. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to validate data derived from the focus group discussion. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Results and Discussions

Offsite impact: past freshwater ecosystem

The respondents opined that the most significant off-site impact is the salinization of previous freshwater rivers and canals. The habitats of aquatic flora of those habitats are also degraded by

increased salinity. The natural vegetation of such areas is being destructed causing major changes in landscapes and biodiversity. Most of the coastal districts already face severe salinity problems, with saline water pushing up to 250 km inward during the dry season. Brackish water from the Bay of Bengal is invading freshwater bodies of *Sheyamnagar*, *Shoronkhola*, *Dacope*, *Morelganj*, *Mongla*, *Rampal* and *Baithaghata* Upazilla. Most of the tree species grown in these areas cannot tolerate high levels of salinity. They are seriously affected when salts concentrate within the root zone. Trees are severely affected when groundwater is close enough to the surface to discharge or concentrate salts. The greatest threat posed by increased salinity in these areas is the loss of both terrestrial and aquatic habitats. The respondents added that salinity has severely affected riparian vegetation because they occupy the lowest parts of the landscape where they get submerged by saline water.

Impact on the pioneer tree species

The respondents added most of the *Sundari* trees (*Heritiera fomes*) are affected by Dieback disease due to increased salinity. Dieback contributes to the loss of canopy coverage and produces weak crowns, with sparse foliage and a good proportion of dead twigs and branches. In most cases, shoots start to die from the top and root systems become poor. The respondents told *Sundari* trees are declining from *Andharmanik*, *Amurbunia*, *Buddhomari*, *Bhola*, *Boroitola*, *Bogi*, *Chandeshwar*, *Choraputia*, *Chandpai*, *Charkhali*, *Dangmari*, *Dumuria*, *Dashervarani*, *Dhansagor*, *Gulishakhali*, *Harbouria*, *Jongra*, *Jeodhara*, *Karamjal*, *Katakhali*, *Kolomtezi*, *Kochikhali*, *Mrigamari*, *Mora Passur*, *Mora Bogi*, *Nangli*, *Nandobala*, *Pashakhali*, *Panirghat*, *Shapla*, *Shoronkhola*, *Supoti* and *Tamulbunia* of *Sundarbans* mangrove. The respondents argued that not only increased salination but also increased anthropogenic disturbances are causal factors of the decline. They apprehended that *Sundari trees* will be extinct from the *Sundarbans* within a couple of decades if this decline continues.

Impact on mangrove palms

The respondents opined that the abundance of *Nypa* palm (*Nypa fruticans*) and Mangrove Date Palm (*Phoenix paludosa*) is declining from *Andharmanik*, *Choraputia*, *Harbouria*, *Jongra*, *Karamjal*, *Mora Passur*, *Nandobala*, *Supoti* and *Tamulbunia* forest areas, due increased

salination. Once, these areas were considered the paradise habitats for the palms. Saline water tides are highly crucial for *Nypa*'s seed dispersal and germination (Rahman 2023e). It occurs most commonly in areas where a mixture of brackish water and freshwater flows (Rahman 2023f).

Changes in species composition

The respondents admitted that the species composition, species richness, natural regeneration, and vertical and horizontal structure of the mangrove are changing due to increased salinity. Salinity causes a major threat to the pioneer species. The vegetation is responding to increased salination through changes in productivity, canopy closure, tree coverage and species diversity, and migration. Salinity weakens the potentiality of natural regeneration by reducing the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. Hence, the tree mortality rate increases. The production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area, net photosynthesis rate, stomata conductance and transpiration rate of leaves are declining. It was noted that Keora (*Sonneratia apetala*) and Bain (*Avicennia Officinalis*) replace Sundari (*Heritiera fomes*), Bain (*Avicennia Officinalis*), Kakra (*Bruguiera gymnorhiza*), Passur (*Xylocarpus mekongensis*) and Dhondul tree (*Xylocarpus granatum*) species.

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